

SURREAL

AI

The surrealists formed an avant garde art movement in Europe between the two world wars. They were influenced by the writings of Sigmund Freud, attempting to render in visual form the workings of unconscious, uncanny or dream-like states. Surrealist art often employed the unexpected, shocking or nonsensical juxtaposition of bizarre objects to render these states of mind and bridge the gap between reality and fantasy. Many surrealists viewed their work as revolutionary and associated with political causes. Key artists contributing to the surrealist movement were Salvador Dali, Yves Tanguy, Rene Magritte, Jean Arp, Joan Miro, Max Ernst, Leonora Carrington and Frida Kahlo.

The collage images presented here were inspired by this art movement. There are many aspects of the current GenAI moment that are surreal: from the ludicrous overblown claims by Big Tech for how these services will improve everyday life or are magical or godlike, to tech oligarchs' fever dreams of 'the singularity' involving superintelligent AI taking over the world. I hand-made the collages on Canva as a way of criticising these narratives, using the surrealist technique of photomontage. Some collages feature graphics made from Canva resources, others use public domain vintage artwork or the Constraint Systems experimental web-based creative tools. No GenAI was used - just simple image editing, cutting and pasting, and positioning.

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